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MARIE SKŁODOWSKA-CURIE ACTIONS

Individual Fellowships (IF)
Call: H2020-MSCA-IF-2017

PART B

“TimeAdapt”

This proposal is to be evaluated as:

EF-ST

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List of Participating Organisations

Participating organisations	Legal Entity Short Name	Academic (tick)	Non-academic (tick)	Country	Dept./ Division / Laboratory	Supervisor	Role of Partner Organisation
<u>Beneficiary</u>							
UPPSALA UNIVERSITET	UPPSALA UNIVERSITET	X		Sweden	Evolutionary Biology Centre (EBC) Department of Organismal Biology Jakobsson Lab	Mattias Jakobsson	

1. Excellence

1.1 Quality and credibility of the research/innovation action

Introduction

Individuals constituting natural populations are genetically different. This **genetic variation determines** the ability of populations to adapt to environmental changes and, ultimately, **their persistence through time**. Thus, the study of genetic diversity of populations has applications to human health, exploited natural (e.g. fisheries) or artificial (e.g. crops) populations, harmful organisms (e.g. infectious diseases, crop pests) and endangered species. The relative importance of **mutation, genetic drift, gene flow and natural selection along the history of a population shape** the structure of **its genetic pool**. Understanding the strength and interactions of these forces is one of the main goals of population genetics, which uses mathematical models to make inferences on these processes from population genetic data.

The archetype of the population genetic study uses current genetic diversity of populations to make inferences on their past history and to predict their evolution (and, eventually, make management plans). However, such an approach attempts to obtain a detailed description of a complex dynamics from a single snapshot. **Time-series population genetic data** offer a powerful way to track genetic changes through time, and **provide a better picture of the processes acting on the population**. Population geneticists have long-ago acknowledged this; however, this kind of approach had remained incidental due to the difficulties for producing such data (with the exception of fast evolving micro-organisms and viruses).

Nowadays, temporal contrasts of population genetic data are of growing interest. **Evolve-and-resequence (E+R) experiments** (reviewed in ¹) study the evolution of artificial populations in the lab, as in ongoing E+R experiments with the **agricultural pest *Drosophila suzukii*** to study the evolutionary processes that promote invasion (A. Estoup, pers. comm.). **Resurrection experiments** (e.g. the Baseline Project²) use seeds collected from natural plant populations at different generations (often over a period of decades) with the main objective of studying their **adaptation to climate change** (e.g. ^{3,P1}).

The integration of **ancient DNA (aDNA)** analysis to **archaeological research** in the last decade has allowed to directly characterize the ancestral genetic pool of current populations of humans. These studies have revealed how **demographic expansions into Europe** at the Palaeolithic, Neolithic and Bronze Age^{4,5} and selective pressures associated to factors such as **diet and pathogens**⁶ have shaped present-day genetic diversity.

A main factor for the success of these studies has been **the development of high-throughput sequencing technologies**, which allow to obtain genome-wide data at a reasonable cost, including non-model organisms or degraded material (such as ancient samples). The new sequencing technologies have dramatically increased the amount of data with a consequent increase of computational effort for their analysis. More importantly, the density of loci studied makes unreasonable the assumption of independence among markers made by most model-based methods developed up to now. **A major challenge in population genomics is scaling up model-based statistical inference**⁷.

State of the art

In recent years, researchers have been actively developing statistical methods for population genomic data. **Methods to infer demography** (i.e. the neutral processes in population genetics) have been proposed based on observed site frequency spectrum likelihood (e.g. ⁸). However, these do not take into account the linkage among markers, because the calculation of the likelihood under a model of coalescence with recombination is very challenging⁹. To overcome this difficulty, one approach is to simplify the models as it has been done for methods

1 Schlötterer *et al.* (2015) [doi:10.1038/hdy.2014.86](https://doi.org/10.1038/hdy.2014.86)

2 Etterson *et al.* (2016) [doi:10.3732/ajb.1500313](https://doi.org/10.3732/ajb.1500313)

3 Franks *et al.* (2016) [doi:10.1111/mec.13615](https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.13615)

4 Skoglund *et al.* (2012) [doi:10.1126/science.1216304](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1216304); Skoglund *et al.* (2014) [doi:10.1126/science.1253448](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1253448); Malmström *et al.* (2015) [doi:10.1098/rstb.2013.0373](https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2013.0373); Günther & Jakobsson (2016) [doi:10.1101/072926](https://doi.org/10.1101/072926)

5 Goldberg *et al.* (2017) [doi:10.1073/pnas.1616392114](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1616392114)

6 Mathieson *et al.* (2015) [doi:10.1038/nature16152](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature16152); Buckley *et al.* (2017) [doi:10.1093/molbev/msx103](https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msx103)

7 Pool *et al.* (2010) [doi:10.1101/gr.079509.108](https://doi.org/10.1101/gr.079509.108)

8 Gutenkunst *et al.* (2009) [doi:10.1371/journal.pgen.1000695](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1000695); Excoffier *et al.* (2013) [doi:10.1371/journal.pgen.1003905](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1003905)

9 Sousa & Hey (2013) [doi:10.1038/nrg3446](https://doi.org/10.1038/nrg3446)

using coalescent hidden Markov models (e.g. ¹⁰). An alternative simplification consists on substituting the calculation of the likelihood for a distance metric between the observed data and data simulated under the model (e.g. ¹¹), a procedure known as likelihood-free inference or **approximate Bayesian computation (ABC)**.

Until recently, the **paradigm for the detection of natural selection** from population genetic data was to assume that genome-wide data inform about the neutral dynamics affecting the population, which could be inferred by using some of the methods outlined in the previous paragraph. Then, regions of the genome affected by selection should present outlier patterns respect to the inferred demographic history. **This scheme is confronted with recent theoretical works** that show that selection affecting linked sites (background selection and selective sweeps) may bias inference of demography¹². **Co-estimation of neutral and selective processes** has been proposed as one potential solution and **simulation-based methods** (i.e. ABC) as the way to achieve it¹³. However, ABC approaches are computationally expensive methods and their implementation in such settings was unrealistic until recently. This has changed with the introduction of **random forests in ABC** (random forests are machine learning regression/classification methods), which can reduce some orders of magnitude the number of simulation required in ABC¹⁴. The application of random forest in ABC to make inferences under population genetics models with selection is yet to be evaluated.

All these advances have been developed with focus on single-time sample data. **Time-series data have received much less attention**; and some recent works on temporal samples use oversimplified models for detecting locus under selection rather than explicitly model the population genetic dynamics of the system⁶. While there has been several studies developing methods for characterizing selection from time-series data (reviewed in ¹⁵), most of them focus only studying a single locus and **none of them address the effects of linked selection** on genome-wide genetic diversity patterns, thus ignoring potential biases¹².

Despite the lack of statistical tools to analyse the temporal genetic data under complex models, studies of human aDNA have known a considerable success in characterising the history of the peopling of Europe. These studies have revealed that the **genetic pool of modern-day Europeans results from the admixture of three groups**^{4,5}: (1) **hunter-gatherers** that first arrived to Europe around 45 000 years ago, (2) **farmers** from Anatolia, who were responsible of the Neolithic transition around 10 000 years ago and (3) **herders** from the Pontic-Caspian Steppe arriving in the Bronze Age, around 5000 years ago. Several loci associated to diet, pigmentation, immunity and height present changes in genetic diversity between these three groups (characterized with aDNA) and modern day populations that suggest the action of selection⁶. These results offer an overall picture of the genetic history of Europe, but many important details are missing: **time, strength and dynamics of adaptation remain unknown**⁶. Model-based statistical inference will be paramount for the understanding of historical factors affecting the genetic adaptation of these populations (e.g. was time of selection associated to climatic events such as the last glacial maximum?) and testing the role of admixture (e.g. including the test for adaptive introgression).

Objectives

- I. **Development of an ABC statistical framework to co-estimate demography and selection** from time-series population genomic data.
- II. **Characterize the recent adaptive evolution in European human populations** from modern and ancient samples.

Overview of the action

In this project I propose to fill this gap in methods for genomic time-series data and, at the same time, to address the joint inference of neutral and selective processes. I plan to develop a hierarchical two-step random forests ABC algorithm similar to the one proposed in ¹⁶ for classical ABC. The first step is a procedure that reveals the demographic history of the population (population size changes, migration rate, etc.) and the genome-wide distribution of fitness effects of mutations. The second step should serve to identify regions of the genome affected by genetic draft and to estimate the age of selective sweeps and the selection coefficients.

¹⁰ Mailund *et al.* (2011) [doi:10.1371/journal.pgen.1001319](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1001319); Schiffels & Durbin (2014) [doi:10.1038/ng.3015](https://doi.org/10.1038/ng.3015)

¹¹ Boitard *et al.* (2016) [doi:10.1371/journal.pgen.1005877](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1005877)

¹² Ewing & Jensen (2016) [doi:10.1111/mec.13390](https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.13390); Schrider *et al.* (2016) [doi:10.1101/047019](https://doi.org/10.1101/047019)

¹³ Bank *et al.* (2014) [doi:10.1016/j.tig.2014.09.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tig.2014.09.010)

¹⁴ Pudlo *et al.* (2016) [doi:10.1093/bioinformatics/btv684](https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btv684); Raynal *et al.* (2017) [arXiv:1605.05537](https://arxiv.org/abs/1605.05537)

¹⁵ Malaspina (2016) [doi:10.1111/mec.13492](https://doi.org/10.1111/mec.13492)

¹⁶ Bazin *et al.* (2010) [doi:10.1534/genetics.109.112391](https://doi.org/10.1534/genetics.109.112391)

The method developed will be applied to genome data from skeletal remains of individuals who lived between 5,000 and 40,000 years ago and from modern-day Europe. Based on demographic models of admixture, I will identify loci under selection, confirming those already identified and potentially discovering new ones. Then, I will estimate the time and strength of selection, allowing to build a chronology of adaptation dynamics for European populations. Finally, the role of admixture will be evaluated by identifying the population origin of beneficial alleles and by estimating parameters of fitness across modern and ancient populations.

Research methodology and approach

The project will be structured in two work-packages (see Implementation) addressing the two different research objectives and with contrasting methodologies. The first work-package (WP1) will focus on the development and evaluation of the proposed ABC approach. Computationally, the method can be divided in three steps, (1) simulation of data under the model, (2) calculation of summaries from the simulated data, and (3) grow random forests to correlate model parameters and summary statistics. For step (1) we will use **SLiM**¹⁷, a flexible forward population genetic simulator. SLiM was developed to efficiently simulate linked selection and has been thoroughly tested, being used in more than 40 publications (e.g.¹²). For step (3) we will use the R package **abcrf** that implements the use of random forest in ABC¹⁴ and is already optimised using parallel computing. We will program the software to step (2) to calculate summary statistics from data. This program will be developed in C or C++ using the application program interface **OpenMP** for parallel computing, to produce a computationally efficient tool. The three steps will be linked by a pipeline combining BASH and R scripts optimized to run on a computer cluster.

The evaluation of the performance of the method will be done in two different ways. First, I will take advantage of two features of random forests, the measure of **variable importance** and the **out-of-bag error**. Variable importance indicates the number of times a summary statistic is used to grow a random forest, allowing the identification of informative statistics. Out-of-bag refers to the simulations excluded at each tree of the forest, which allow estimating the prior error of the regression forest. In addition, SLiM will be used to simulate additional datasets (**pseudo-observed dataset, POD**) that will be analysed with the method, comparison of the known (simulated) truth and the estimates will show the **power and false positive rate** for the identification of loci under selection and the **error** in the estimates of selection and demographic parameters. Models used to simulate PODs will include departures from the inference model (e.g. POD from an expanding population analysed under an inference model of constant size) to evaluate the **robustness** of the method. A demographic model of population admixture will be specifically evaluated for the application of the method in the second work-package (WP2).

WP2 will be dedicated to improve our understanding of the adaptive history of human populations in Europe by applying the methods developed in WP1. This will be achieved by analysing public data (ancient, see www.oagr.org.au, and modern samples, see www.internationalgenome.org) and data generated at the Jakobsson lab as part of other funded projects (current proposal does not include the generation of new data). The multiple datasets will be treated with **bioinformatic** tools (e.g. SAMtools) to make them uniform in format and filter criteria. The data will be summarized to statistics identified as informative for the inference of demographic history and selection in WP1.

Previous knowledge of the European human population will be used to define a demographic model (including the admixture of among the three ancient groups: hunter-gatherers, farmers and Pontic-steppe herders) and prior probability distributions for the parameter of this model⁴. Selection processes will be modelled taken into account current knowledge on distribution of fitness effects of new mutations in human populations¹⁸ and hypothesis of adaptation to the natural environment and diet⁶. Applying the random forests ABC approach I will obtain estimates of the **demographic parameters** of the models plus **genome-level** (e.g. distribution of fitness effects) and **locus-specific** (selection coefficient of a given mutation) **selection parameters**. In addition to the parameters of the model, other features of the model that can be measured in the simulations, such as the **mutation load** of populations and other fitness-derived measures, will be estimated across ancient groups and along time. Results will be interpreted in the light of current knowledge from archaeology, geology and climatology.

Originality and innovative aspects of the research programme

The main originality of the proposal is to address the **joint inference of neutral and selective processes**. Disentangling the effects of linked selection and demography is a long-standing difficulty in population genetics

¹⁷ Messer (2013) [doi:10.1534/genetics.113.152181](https://doi.org/10.1534/genetics.113.152181)

¹⁸ Lohmueller (2014) [doi:10.1016/j.gde.2014.09.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gde.2014.09.005)

that seems to start to ease with the current wealth of genomic data¹⁹. Regarding this point, **our results will be of general interest to evolutionary biologists** beyond their application to the analysis of time series data. **The timeliness of our project is highlighted by the recent development of random forests ABC** that alleviates the computational burden of complex simulations (population genetics that include the effects of selection on linked sites). Our project has the additional leverage of using **temporal contrasts** of genomic data in a **model organism** (i.e. in the sense of a species that has been widely studied, humans are not model organisms *sensu stricto*), which provides much more information of the evolutionary processes studied than the average population genetic study. To this respect, ABC approach has been shown to be able to estimate the demography from time series data and to identify loci under selection in models assuming multiple independent loci²⁰. I will extend ABC inference to the case of linked loci and presence of background selection.

The topic of our proposal lays in the **intersection of genetics and statistics** by using tool of **computer science** for the development of the theoretical work. The project will analyse actual genomic time-series data from modern and ancient human populations, which will require the interaction with **archaeologists** and **anthropologists** (working at Jakobsson lab or part of his collaboration network) for a interdisciplinary interpretation of the results.

Regarding the gender dimension of the project, there is some small differences to be taken into account in our models. Uni-parentally inherited loci (i.e. Y chromosome, mitochondrial DNA) will be modelled taking into account their inheritance transmission. Some differences would be expected between those markers and loci at autosomal chromosomes if there is sex biased dispersal, as seems to have been the case in the Bronze age admixture events⁶. Note, in addition, that at the Jakobsson lab and at the advisory committee there will be an appropriate gender balance (see below).

1.2 Quality and appropriateness of the training and of the two way transfer of knowledge between the researcher and the host

The main training objective of the fellowship is to strengthen the skills that will allow me to develop a research program in population genomics using state-of-the-art data production. My current position, within a purely theoretical research team, makes sparse the interactions with empirical biologists. In contrast, it has given the opportunity to grow my analytical skills. I expect that my integration to the Jakobsson Lab, which combines both theoretical and empirical work, will be fruitful for both parties through the following interactions:

Training on high throughput sequencing technologies. During my PhD I was involved in wet lab work, including Sanger sequencing. After that I have been mainly involved in data analysis for different molecular markers but I have no direct experience with the new sequencing technology datasets. By integrating a research team that uses these technologies I will participate to meetings and discussions regarding the strategy of sequencing different samples for different objectives, which will help me to deepen my understanding on the specificities and advantages of each technology. In addition, I will learn to perform the bioinformatic treatment of the raw data, not only because I will need to handle the data by myself during the project (training by practice) but also because this treatment may introduce biases on the final data than may require to be included in the simulation models I will develop.

Training on model organisms genetics. Studying the population genetics of humans, a model organism in the genetic sense, will be an enriching experience to me. I have been working mostly with non-model organisms, for which there is neither reference genome nor gene annotation. This limited knowledge hampers many types of analysis. Direct experience in methods using this kind of information (such as the identification of coding loci to build site frequency spectra for silent and non-silent sites) will prepare me to a near future when, due to the increasingly cheaper sequencing technologies, this information will be available even for non-model organisms.

Training on programming. Most of my programming work over the years has been based on using R language. While R is a powerful tool for statistics, it suffers from low computational efficiency. For the current project I will require to work with a programming language such as C or C++ to produce computationally efficient code. Although I have some previous experience in C programming, I will take a course on programming during the first months of my fellowship to improve my skills and assure a better product. The Department of Information Technology at Uppsala University (UU) provides courses in English on Scientific Computing at different levels including a course in Object Oriented Programming with C++.

¹⁹ Josephs & Wright (2016) [doi:10.1371/journal.pgen.1006240](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1006240)

²⁰ Foll *et al.* (2015) [doi:10.1111/1755-0998.12280](https://doi.org/10.1111/1755-0998.12280)

Training on professional skills. Integrating a new work environment will be an excellent opportunity to enhance many general skills, such as teamwork and management of a budget. Communication skills, particularly in English language, will improve due to my daily life interaction with workmates and by presenting my work to colleagues (seminars), students (see planned postgraduate course) and the general public (SciFest and European Researcher Night, see below). In addition I will take the Group Leadership Training (8 day-long seances once per month) offered by UU to its staff.

Transference of knowledge on Approximate Bayesian Computation. In the last ten years I have been working on population genetic inference methods based on ABC^{P2,P3,P4,P5,P7,P8,P9} and I have participated in research projects with the statisticians that have developed the application of random forests to ABC¹³ (who are colleagues from the Computational Biology Institute in Montpellier). I will transfer my know-how on ABC random forests through my interactions with the members of M. Jakobsson team. In addition I will give a presentation open to all researchers at the Evolutionary Biology Centre and I will prepare a postgraduate-level course on ABC. I have already the experience and materials available for such a course (see teaching section in CV) that has already allowed several researchers to incorporate this technique to their toolbox.

Networking among researchers from Uppsala and Montpellier. My stay in Jakobsson Lab can also catalyse the development of interactions among researcher from Montpellier and Uppsala, two important centers for evolutionary biology research in Europe. In particular, research interests of my current team colleagues (A. Estoup, M. Gauthier, R. Leblois, R. Vitalis; who develop statistical methods for population genetics) are overlapping with the theoretical work done at Jakobsson Lab and our project can bring new opportunities of collaboration among them.

Stop-motion animation for science communication films. I will encourage lab members to be involved in my project of film making (see below), which will introduce them to the techniques of stop-motion animation but also to more general skills such as the use of sound and film edition software.

1.3 Quality of the supervision and of the integration in the team/institution

Professor Mattias Jakobsson (h-index=26, 63 publications, 4480 total citations) runs a laboratory studying population genetics and human evolution. His group develops two lines of research relevant to this project: the **study of human evolutionary and demographic history from ancient DNA** and **theoretical population genetics and development of statistical inference methods**. To this respect, the Jakobsson Lab offers the best possible environment to develop my research project as this combination of research interests is found in very few laboratories. The team is composed by 8 staff researchers, 2 postdocs, 9 PhD students and 2 engineers and research assistants (with a good gender balance: 8 male/13 female); previous members of the lab included 5 PhD students, 5 master students and 4 visiting researchers, which shows M. Jakobsson's substantial experience in supervising a research team. The product of their research are more than 70 publications among the most prestigious generalist and specialist journals (e.g. 5 in *Science*, 4 in *Nature*, 4 in *PNAS*, 9 in *Molecular Biology and Evolution*). M. Jakobsson work has been funded with an **European Research Council Starting Grant** (2012), a Swedish Research Council **grant for Distinguished Young Researchers** (2013), the **Wallenberg Academy Fellowship** (2013) and the **Göran Gustavsson Prize** (2015). M. Jakobsson is the one of the coordinators of the **Atlas of Ancient Human Genomes in Sweden** project (www.theatlas.se), funded by the Swedish Foundation for Humanities and Social Sciences and the Swedish Research Council and the **1000 Ancient Genome project**, funded by the Knut & Alice Wallenberg Foundation.

As a member of the Jakobsson Lab I will participate to their weekly meetings and I will contribute to the organisation of seminars and to the mentoring of master and PhD students. Three of the researchers in the lab (M. Jakobsson, P. Sjödin, T. Günther) have a strong background in mathematics and computational biology and I will interacting with them for the development of my work. Bioinformatic support in the group is assured by a research assistant. Regarding science communication and outreach, these activities are coordinated by O. Thalmann for the lab. The lab organise regularly social events (*fika*, cultural or sport outings) that promote the cohesion among lab member and will help me to integrate in the group.

The Jakobsson Lab belongs to the **Evolutionary Biology Centre** (EBC), Scandinavia's largest evolutionary biology research centre. Prominent members of the EBC include Hans Ellegren, Martin Lascoux who work on research topics (evolutionary biology and population genomics) related to our proposal. At the EBC weekly seminar series "Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution", internationally renowned speakers present their latest work, which will offer an excellent opportunity for discussing science with international actors and extend my network.

At a more general level, the **International Faculty and Staff Services** (EURAXESS Centre) at UU organises a number of activities, including welcome seminars, information meetings, Swedish language courses and social activities that will help me in my integration into the Swedish culture and everyday life (including tax, insurance and childcare administrative procedures).

1.4 Capacity of the researcher to reach or re-enforce a position of professional maturity/independence

Since the beginning of my research career I have chosen mobility as a way to learn and diversify my skills. I moved to England to do my PhD thesis on empirical population genetics and, by my own initiative, I started to complement the empirical work with theoretical simulation-based work. I got more interested in developing statistical methods and I obtained a European Science Foundation exchange grant to develop my own project in a short stay in Brussels. Later on, when I was hired as a postdoc at the CNRS in Paris, I continued to maintain the collaboration network I had built over the years in England, Belgium and Spain^{P3,P8,P12,P16}. These have been very productive periods of my career that have pushed me to learn new skills, such as programming; improve my professional skills, and learn two foreign languages (English and French).

At present, I have a solid position as a researcher, with a growing network of collaborators. However, in order to continue growing as a researcher, I need to reinforce my research objectives. I will continue developing statistical tools and using simulations to answer questions in evolutionary biology (in particular, to study the evolutionary consequences of mating systems, such as selfing), but I want to integrate these approaches into an empirical research line that will guide them. To this respect, M. Jakobsson will be a role model as he has done a somehow similar transition from a background in mathematics into a leading position in the field of human evolutionary genetics.

In addition, Uppsala University offers support for career development to its staff in several ways, including **courses on professional skills** (e.g. Group Leadership Training) and **personal coaching**. I will use these services to build a **career development plan** that will help me in my path to develop my own empirical research line.

2. Impact

2.1 *Enhancing the potential and future career prospects of the researcher*

As a biologist developing statistical methods, my work has a pivotal role in research by building a bridge that brings together mathematicians and biologists. However, this comes with a cost, since I am often seen as a statistician by biologists and vice-versa, and this has negative implications on the success to obtain funding as a project leader. In order to become a Senior Researcher (*Directeur de Recherche*, in French) at my home institution, substantial experience in leading research projects and supervising students and postdocs is required. A revision of my career and research objectives incites me towards a reorientation of my work towards more empirical work. The Marie Skłodowska-Curie (MSC) fellowship will play a key role in this transition: (1) I will acquire experience on state-of-the-art sequencing technologies. This technology has changed dramatically in the last ten years and new advances are still expected in the years to come. Proper planning of a research project in empirical population genetics requires a good knowledge of the pros and cons of the different technologies available and expertise in the bioinformatic treatment of the data is necessary to execute the research. (2) I will integrate into a research group that combines both empirical and theoretical research. This will give me an opportunity to learn about the management and integration of these two different research lines. (3) My research visibility will increase. The study of human populations is in the cutting-edge of the field of population genetics, which will allow me to interact with the main actors of the field of computational and human population genetics (e.g. Rasmus Nielsen, Noah Rosenberg, Laurent Excoffier) and publish in top ranked journals. In addition, my stay in Uppsala will allow me to interact with potential future collaborators such as Carina Schlebusch and Martin Lascoux (see section 3.3). C. Schlebusch studies African human populations and has recently started work on ancient samples²¹; she would be interested in applying the methods I develop in the near future. Martin Lascoux is a plant population geneticist working on the shepherd's purse (*Capsella bursa-pastoris*) a model for the evolution of selfing.

In summary, my stay in the Jakobsson Lab will provide me with experience and contacts that will increase my chances to lead national and international projects, will extend my international network of collaborators and will enhance my research profile, putting me in the best position to build my own research group on theoretical and empirical genetics of population of plants with mixed mating systems.

2.2 *Quality of the proposed measures to exploit and disseminate the action results*

²¹ Schlebusch et al. (2017) [doi:10.1101/145409](https://doi.org/10.1101/145409)

The results of the project will be published in **international peer-reviewed journals**. I expect at least three publications from the results (deliverables D1.1, D1.2 and D2.2, see below). The objectives addressed should interest high ranking journal in the field (e.g. *Molecular Biology and Evolution*, *PLoS Genetics*) and, potentially, top international generalist journals (e.g. *Science*, *Nature*). Previous to publication, pre-prints will be made available at public repositories such as [bioRxiv](#) (articles deposited in bioRxiv are announced in Twitter and in the specialised blog [Haldane's Sieve](#), which are followed by a big proportion of the evolutionary biology scientific community). The software produced (deliverable D1.3) and any other code used for the development of other tasks, will be made publicly available in specialized repositories, such as [Zenodo](#), under a **GNU General Public License** or equivalent.

Every year, I will attend at least one scientific **international conference** such as the ones organized by the **Society for Molecular Biology and Evolution** (biannual meeting) or the **European Society for Evolutionary Biology** (biannual meeting). In addition, I will also present my results to specific research communities: computational biologists at meetings such as the [Mathematical and Computational Evolutionary Biology](#) (annual meeting), human evolutionary biologists at meetings such as the [European Society for the study of Human Evolution meeting](#) (annual meeting) and archaeologist at meeting such as the [European Association of Archaeologists meeting](#) (annual meeting). I will show my results favouring oral presentation when possible (poster contributions will be also made available at [figshare](#)).

Major achievements of the project will be announced through the Jakobsson Lab web-page (news section) and through the [ResearchGate](#) portal.

2.3 *Quality of the proposed measures to communicate the action activities to different target audiences*

Stop-motion animation films: In order to communicate the results of our work to the general public I plan to produce at least two short (5-10 minutes) animated films that will be available at the Jakobsson Lab webpage and in a YouTube channel specially created for this purpose. The first will be an introductory film about the research conducted in the lab, combining biology and history, genetics and archaeology, to reveal the evolutionary trajectory and history of human populations. The objective of this film is to be an introduction to a series of more specific films that will focus on particular achievements of the research produced in the lab. A second film, produced towards the end of my stay, will present the results of my research project. Members of the lab will be encouraged to participate in the film making so they can learn the techniques involved and later on produce a film on their research (possibly with my help). Stop-motion technique is chosen as a cheap, effective and visually attractive way to make animations of complex processes and because of my previous experience with that medium (see CV). At least two versions, in Swedish and in English, will be produced for each film.

Public engagement during science festivals: I will present my research project in science festivals such as the European Researchers' Night and [Uppsala University SciFest](#). UU SciFest is a yearly, multilingual Science Festival is organised by UU since 2011. It consists on a three-day educational event that includes shows, demonstrations and hands-on activities allowing children and general public to experience research and science. I will prepare a stand showing materials and diagrams explaining our work and prepare time-capsules with groups of school children as an analogy of the work we pursue.

3. **Quality and Efficiency of the Implementation**

3.1 *Coherence and effectiveness of the work plan*

The project is divided in two work-packages separating the theoretical developments (WP1, methodological deliverables of interest in evolutionary genomics) and empirical data analyses (WP2, deliverables of interest for human and ancient DNA research community). The schedule of the project is determined by the development of key procedures for the achievement of the final objectives of the project, starting from the more general to the more specific: (1) the two-step ABC algorithm with random forest (M1.1); (2) summary statistics for co-estimation of demography and selection (M1.2); (3) post-mortem DNA damage model and other specific biases (M2.1). Transversal to these advances is the development of a software pipeline that implements them (M1.3).

Work-package 1: Development of an ABC statistical framework to co-estimate demography and selection from time-series population genomic data.

Task 1.1: Adapting the two-step ABC algorithm to random forests ABC.

Description: The two-step ABC algorithm is based on the capacity to sample from the genome-wide parameter posterior distributions obtained in the first step to perform the inference of locus-specific parameters in the second

step. Sampling directly from the marginal distribution does not take into account the correlations among parameters, it is necessary to sample from their joint distribution. In rejection based ABC this is done by re-sampling on the parameter values for the simulations closest to the observed data, i.e. the simulation in the neighbourhood of the observed data. In random forests there is also a notion of neighbourhood that is defined by the simulations that share the same leaf in any regression tree of the forest²². However, because the posterior distribution of each parameter is obtained by a different forest, a different neighbourhood is defined for each parameter. Can these neighbourhoods be exploited to sample from an approximation of the joint posterior distribution of parameters? We expect that these neighbourhoods will be overlapping to a certain degree, allowing to devise an algorithm to sample parameter values from them. Alternatively, the vector of parameters might be sampled from a multivariate normal with the means and covariance matrix obtained from first ABC step as described in random forest ABC¹⁴.

Deliverable D1.1: A comparison among alternative ways to sample from the joint posterior probability distribution of parameters, from ABC random forest and from rejection-based ABC

Task 1.2: Finding informative summary statistics for co-estimation of genome-wide demography and selection effects.

Description: ABC uses a distance measure between observed data and simulated data as a proxy for the likelihood. In order to calculate this distance summary statistics that contain information about the modelled process are used. Informative summary statistics for the estimation of demography are well known as this has been the main application of ABC. However, appropriate summary statistics to make inferences on genome wide patterns of selection have never been tested in the context of ABC and need to be identified. I will evaluate statistics such as the ones based on the site frequency spectrum of different site categories (e.g. silent and non-silent sites) as proposed in ²³ that are informative about the distribution of fitness effects of mutations and the fraction of adaptive substitutions. To this end, random forests measures of variable importance will allow me classifying summary statistics by its informativeness to each parameter of the model¹⁴.

Deliverable D1.2: Informative summary statistics for inference of genome-wide selection parameters (ranked according to their informativeness)

Task 1.3: Development of software and pipeline of analysis.

Description: This task is, in fact, transversal to the other described tasks. It is of more technical nature and consists on the implementation of results from tasks 1.1, 1.2 and 2.1, in addition to some additional developments, into a software pipeline. Its main output will be software allowing the application of the methods developed during the project. The pipeline will:

- sample parameters from prior probability distributions (in R),
- run simulations (using SLiM¹⁸),
- simulate ancient DNA damage and sequencing technologies bias (if necessary) (task 2.1),
- calculate summary statistics (identified in task 1.2), the software for this step will be also developed as part of the project,
- perform random forest ABC for genome wide inference (in R),
- sample from posterior probability distributions (algorithm developed in task 1.1),
- simulate single locus trajectories (SLiM)
- and perform again random forest ABC for single locus inference (in R).

Deliverable D1.3: A software pipeline implementing methods resulted from tasks 1.1, 1.2 and 2.1

Work-package 2: Characterize the recent genetic evolution in European human populations from modern and ancient samples.

Task 2.1: Adaptation of the methods to the specificities of the data analysed.

Description: WP1 is focused on general developments and its results will be evaluated under ideal conditions with simulated data. Real data, however, differ from these ideal situations mainly due to sequencing error rate and biases, and post-mortem DNA damage (for the case of ancient DNA). To take them into account in the ABC framework, simulated data (without error) needs to be modified to include these features expected in real data.

²² Lin & Jean (2006) [doi:10.1198/016214505000001230](https://doi.org/10.1198/016214505000001230)

²³ Eyre-Walker & Keightley (2009) [doi:10.1093/molbev/msp119](https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msp119)

This will be done through simulations using already described models for sequencing error rate (e.g. ²⁴) and aDNA damage (e.g. ²⁵).

Task 2.2: Analysis of modern and ancient DNA data from human populations.

Description: The current composition of the European gene pool is mainly composed of the contribution of the early hunter-gatherers that arrived to the continent plus the contribution of to later demographic waves arriving at the Neolithic transition (farmers from Anatolia) and the Bronze age (Pontic-steppe herders). These groups co-existed during long periods of time at different parts of Europe. Interaction between them gave result to the admixed groups from which modern populations derive^{5,6}. I will apply the methods developed in this project to these (and yet unpublished) data in order to investigate the adaptive changes undergone by modern human populations, in particular dating selective sweeps and testing the adaptive role of local introgression among groups.

Deliverable D2.2: Chronology of the adaptation history of European human populations. Identification of the contribution of the three ancient groups to the adaptation to diet, pathogens and environment.

Milestones

M1.1: An algorithm to sample from the joint posterior probability distribution of parameters is identified

M1.2: Summary statistics that allow co-estimation of demography and selection processes at genome-wide level are identified

M1.3: A complete software pipeline implements all the methods developed in the project

M2.1: Specific features of target data (e.g. post-mortem aDNA damage) are included in the software pipeline

Gantt Chart

Month (assuming start at September 2018)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
RESEARCH PROJECT																								
Work-package 1: Development method																								
Task 1.1: Two-step ABC algorithm																								
Task 1.2: Summary stats for co-estimation																								
Task 1.3: Pipeline development																								
Work-package 2: Inferences from aDNA																								
Task 2.1: Post-mortem DNA damage model																								
Task 2.2: Inferences from empirical data																								
Deliverable																								
Milestone																								
TRAINING																								
Advanced programming course																								
Course on Group Leadership																								
DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS																								
Writing articles (for specialists)																								
Contributions to international conferences																								
Postgraduate course on ABC																								
Film making																								
Science Festivals																								

3.2 Appropriateness of the allocation of tasks and resources

Time and budget resources are appropriate and sufficient to reach our objectives. Our proposal is based on theoretical, simulation-based work. Computing facilities (UPPMAX cluster) are available free of charge for UU projects. The budget will be mostly dedicated for purchasing a performant computer workstation for personal use, paying publication costs (favouring open-access) and expenses for participating to international conferences. Other costs include the acquisition of software licences for research and film making and course fees (i.e. training in advanced programming).

Regarding time allocation, most of the work time will be consumed by the development of software (task 1.3), which will occupy me most of the first year and a half, leaving the reaming six months to concentrate in the analysis and interpretation of human population data. Another factor affecting the duration of tasks is the computing cost of simulations. Task 1.1 will be based on coalescent simulations and should be quick to complete (and compatible with taking a programming course at the same time). Task 2.1 will build on previously simulated data (only post simulation data modifications are developed) and should not be time consuming. More time,

²⁴ Huang *et al.* (2012) [doi:10.1093/bioinformatics/btr708](https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btr708)

²⁵ Briggs *et al.* (2007) [doi:10.1073/pnas.0704665104](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0704665104)

however, has been allocated to task 1.2 which will include most of the forward-time simulations. Additional time exclusive for task 1.3 has been planned to allow for software development features not included in other tasks *per se* (e.g. single locus simulation and ABC inference). Film making will take around one week full-time for each short film.

3.3 *Appropriateness of the management structure and procedures, including risk management*

I will be responsible of the management of the project with the help and supervision of M. Jakobsson. We will have meetings every two weeks to discuss the project. Dates of expected time of achievement for each milestone will be used as a guide to control the adequate progress of the work. An external advisory committee, formed by Carina Schlebusch and Martin Lascoux, will be set up to have an external evaluation of the progress every six months (meetings will be set up to coincide with the anticipated dates of milestone achievements whenever possible). M. Jakobsson will supervise the programming work and will advise about specific programming courses that will be helpful for completing my training and the project.

I have identified two risks linked to the achievement of milestones M1.1 and M1.2. There is low risk for not being able to reach milestone M1.1 in time: while it would be ideal to identify an algorithm to sample from the neighbourhood defined by the random forests, it is reasonable to assume that an alternative sampling from a multivariate probability distribution will capture the essence of the joint posterior distribution of parameters. The risk to not be able to reach M1.2 is the potential lack of information of data to co-estimate demography and selection at genome wide level. I believe this to be unlikely, because procedures to make such inferences separately have already been described and use different type of information from the data. Nevertheless, if that would be the case, the project would explore two alternatives: (1) separating demography from selection at genomic level is not possible, but this uncertainty could be integrated in the inference at the locus specific level; and (2) returning to a classical scheme where genome wide data is assumed to be influenced by demography only. A dangerous risk resides in not reaching milestone M1.3 on time since the most important anticipated results of the project depend on the completion of the software pipeline in a reasonable time. While the consequences of this failure to achieve M1.3 are very important, it will be unlikely given my programming experience and the support offered by the host laboratory from three computational biologist (M. Jakobsson, P. Sjödin and T. Günther) and a bioinformatician (A. Munters). Nevertheless, we will be vigilant to complete it on time, the progress of Task 1.3 will be discussed in all meetings to assure. In case of an important delay in the development of the pipeline, the completion of the pipeline would be given priority to the addition of features (e.g. adding the calculation of more summary statistics). Some features, such as the simulation of sequencing error and aDNA damage (milestone M2.1), could be sacrificed *in extremis* and substitute them with a more stringent bioinformatic filtering of data, as it is currently performed with aDNA as routine in the lab.

3.4 *Appropriateness of the institutional environment (infrastructure)*

The host department has a support team composed by administrative staff, personnel officers, system administrator, librarian and a manager. They have experience managing European projects including MSC fellowships (the Evolutionary Biology Center has hosted at least 9 individual MSC fellowships). They will arrange all practical aspects of my incorporation to the Jakobsson Lab, including assignment of office space, access to computing facilities and to on-line bibliographic resources.

Additional computing facilities will available at the Uppsala Multidisciplinary Centre for Advanced Computational Science (UPPMAX) which has a cluster with more than 2 000 000 CPU hours per month of total capacity, and the Jakobsson Lab regularly and consistently use 300,000 CPU hours/month.

The Jakobsson Lab has state-of-the-art facilities for the production of high throughput sequencing data from ancient and modern human samples. Although, the present project does not involve any use of these facilities or data production, the genomic data has already been, and continues to be, produced in the lab, and guarantees an abundance of data available for analysis with the developed methods.

4. CV of the Experienced Researcher

My research career started as an **empirical population geneticist** studying the endemic Canary Island pine. In order to understand the **colonization of the archipelago and the role of volcanism, environment and human activities in shaping the genetic diversity of the pine forest** I employed molecular markers (microsatellites)^{P17,P19}. Soon I understood the utility of completing the analyses with theoretical work based on coalescent simulations^{P20,P21}. Ultimately, this led me to a **transition to simulation-based work and development of statistical method** in population genetics.

During my postdoc years I addressed several questions. First, I studied the role of clonality in the maintenance of the self-incompatibility (SI) systems by means of simulations. In these simulations I put in evidence a **hitch-hiking process between** the S locus (locus responsible for SI) and **physically unlinked loci** under negative selection in highly-clonal small populations^{P13}. While this was a short project, it awoke in me a strong interest on the **effect of mating system on the dynamics of adaptation** that would lead me to focus later on selfing species (see below). Regarding statistical methods, I developed approaches (1) to **distinguish between gene flow and incomplete lineage sorting** as the origin of shared polymorphism between populations^{P6}, (2) to estimate of mutation rates from population genetic and father-son transmission data (this publication has become a key **reference for mutation rates at the human Y chromosome microsatellites** used in forensic and demographic analysis)^{P10} and (3) to make inferences on population size changes through time^{P2,P16}. During this period I also first addressed question regarding temporal genetic data showing that the **time dependency of molecular rates hypothesis**²⁶ **could be alternatively or partially explained by violations of the inference model**^{P15}.

With the recruitment in my current institution, I integrated a group of researches working on the development of statistical methods for population genetics (since 2015 I have management responsibilities in the group). Initially, I focused my work on methods based on **approximate Bayesian computation** (e.g. ^{P2,P5}), applying my developments to data from different collaborators (e.g. ^{P3,P4,P7,P8,P9,P11}). Among these works it is worth mention the phylogeographic analysis of wild olives which suggests a **northern Levant origin for the domestication of the olive tree**^{P7}.

In the last years I have worked studying the adaptation dynamics of selfing plants by means of temporal contrasts. Because of the effects in the reduction of genetic diversity and recombination, **selfing is considered an evolutionary dead end**. Can selfing species quickly adapt to environmental changes? In collaboration with researchers performing resurrection experiments in *Arabidopsis thaliana* and *Medicago truncatula*, I have developed genome scans adapted to temporal data to detect loci under recent selection (software TempoDiff). First results in *A. thaliana* have been recently published showing the **fast action of selection and the role of pleiotropyin adaptation**^{P1}. Further work currently in preparation include an evaluation of the method and its limits for the application to highly selfing populations (90% completed) and an application to *M. truncatula* populations (90% completed).

However, my interaction with empirical geneticists comes at a late stage of research projects (data analysis). The MSC fellowship will allow me to integrate a research groups doing both molecular work and methodological developments. This experience will be very valuable for making a new transition in my career towards more empirical work, allowing me to **gain independence in my research projects** and pursue a research line on the effects of mating systems combining both empirical and theoretical work.

Personal data

Full name: Miguel de Navascués Melero

Year of birth: 1978

Family status: Married, one child (born 2013)

Languages: Spanish (mother tongue), English (fluent), French (fluent), Italian (proficient)

Personal web page: <http://sites.google.com/site/navascuesresearch/>

ResearcherID: [C-8705-2009](#)
 ORCID: [0000-0001-8342-6047](#)

Career

2015–present **Co-organizer** of the [Statistical and Evolutionary Population Genomics](#) team at the Centre de Biologie et de Gestion des Populations (Montpellier, France)
 2012–present **Researcher**. [Computational Biology Institute](#) (Montpellier, France)
 2009–present **Researcher**. INRA-UMR Centre de Biologie et de Gestion des Populations (Montpellier, France)
 2007–2009 **Postdoc**. CNRS-UMR Écologie et Évolution (Paris, France)
 2006–2007 **Visiting researcher**. Université Libre de Bruxelles (Belgium)
 2006 **Researcher** (fixed-term contract). Universidad Politécnica de Madrid & Centro de Investigación Forestal-INIA (Spain)
 2001–2006 **PhD** Degree in Biological Sciences. University of East Anglia (UK)
 1996–2001 Licenciatura en Ciencias Biológicas (equivalent to **BSc+MSc**) Universidad Autónoma de Madrid (Spain)

Funded projects

2016–2019 GENOMEHARVEST: Mobilizing biomathematics/bioinformatics and genomics/genetics to decipher genome organization and dynamics as pathways to crop improvement. Agropolis Fondation flagship project. *Role: Co-applicant*
 2016–2017 PLANTEVOL: Plant biodiversity in sub-Antarctic Islands: evolution, past and future in changing environments. Institut Paul-Emile Victor. *Role: Co-applicant*
 2014–2018 TRIPTIC: *Trichogramma* for the protection of crops: genomics, life history traits and installation capacity. ANR 2014. *Role: Co-applicant*
 2014 Contribution of RAD markers to phylogenetics: the case of genus *Thaumetopoea*. Projet Innovant EFPA 2014. *Role: Co-principal investigator*
 2014–2015 Interaction between ecological processes within community and population genetic structure. Programme PHC Tournesol. *Role: Host for visiting researcher*
 2013–2016 SELFADAPT: Adaptation to climate change under selfing - experimental test and selection footprints in *Medicago truncatula*. Meta-programme INRA - Adapting Agriculture and Forestry to Climate Change 2012. *Role: Co-coordinator*
 2012–2017 IBC: Computational Biology Institute. ANR Investissements d'Avenir, Bioinformatique 2011. *Role: Co-applicant*
 2010–2013 IGGIPOP: Statistics inference in Population Genetics and Genomics. Jeune Équipe INRA 2010. *Role: Co-applicant*
 2009–2011 EMILE: Study of Inferential Methods and Software for Evolution. ANR. *Role: Co-applicant*
 2006–2007 Developing Statistical Tools for Detection of Historical Demographic Expansions with Linked Microsatellites. European Science Foundation, CONGEN Exchange Grant. *Role: Principal investigator*

Publication statistics

21 publications with total citations: 508 (382 since 2012)
 h-index: 10 (WoS=Web of Science), 13 (GS=Google Scholar)
 i10-index: 14 (GS)

Publications (self-citations removed) (* corresponding author)

- P1 Frachon, Libourel, Villoutreix, Carrère, Glorieux, Huard-Chauveau, [Navascués](#), Gay, Vitalis, Baron, Amsellem, Bouchez, Vidal, Le Corre, Roby, Bergelson & Roux (2017) Intermediate degrees of synergistic pleiotropy drive adaptive evolution in ecological time. *Nature Ecology & Evolution* [doi:10.1038/s41559-017-0297-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-017-0297-1)
- P2 *[Navascués](#), Leblois & Burgarella (2017) Demographic inference through approximate-Bayesian-computation skyline plots. *PeerJ* [doi:10.7717/peerj.3530](https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.3530)
- P3 Budde, González-Martínez, [Navascués](#), Burgarella, Mosca, Lorenzo, Zabal-Aguirre, Vendramin, Verdú, Pausas, Heuertz (2017) Neutral and adaptive population genetic effects of high fire frequency at regional and local scales in *Pinus halepensis* Mill. *Annals of Botany* [doi:10.1093/aob/mcw286](https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcw286)
- P4 Berthier, Garba, Leblois, [Navascués](#), Tatard, Gauthier, Gagaré, Piry, Brouat, Dalecky, Loiseau & Dobigny (2016) Black rat invasion of inland Sahel: insights from interviews and population genetics in South Western Niger. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society* [doi:10.1111/bij.12836](https://doi.org/10.1111/bij.12836)
1 citation
- P5 Illera, Palmero, Laiolo, Rodríguez, Moreno & [Navascués](#) (2014) Genetic, morphological and acoustic evidence reveals lack of diversification in the colonization process in an island bird. *Evolution* [doi:10.1111/evo.12429](https://doi.org/10.1111/evo.12429)
4 citations
- P6 *[Navascués](#), Legrand, Campagne, Cariou & Depaulis (2014) Distinguishing migration from isolation using genes with intragenic recombination: detecting introgression in the *Drosophila simulans* species complex. *BMC Evolutionary Biology* [doi:10.1186/1471-2148-14-89](https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2148-14-89)
3 citations
- P7 Besnard, Khadari, [Navascués](#), Fernández-Mazuecos, El Bakkali, Arrigo, Baali-Cherif, Brunini-Bronzini de Caraffa, Santoni, Vargas & Savolainen (2013) The complex history of the olive tree: from Late Quaternary diversification of Mediterranean lineages to primary domestication in the northern Levant. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* [doi:10.1098/rspb.2012.2833](https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2012.2833)
63 citations, WoS Highly Cited Paper (Plant & Animal Science)
- P8 Burgarella, [Navascués](#), Zabal-Aguirre, Berganzo, Riba, Mayol, Vendramin & González-Martínez (2012) Recent population decline and selection shape diversity of taxol-related genes. *Molecular Ecology* [doi:10.1111/j.1365-294X.2012.05532.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2012.05532.x)
7 citations (WoS/GS)
- P9 Lakis, [Navascués](#), Rekima, Simon, Remigereau, Leveugle, Takvorian, Lamy, Depaulis & Robert (2012) Evolution of neutral and flowering genes along pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) domestication. *PLoS ONE* [doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0036642](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0036642)
6 citations (WoS/GS)
- P10 Burgarella & *[Navascués](#) (2011) Mutation rate estimates for 110 Y-chromosome STRs combining population and father-son pair data. *European Journal of Human Genetics* [doi:10.1038/ejhg.2010.154](https://doi.org/10.1038/ejhg.2010.154)
24 citations (WoS/GS)
- P11 Duminil, Heuertz, Doucet, Bourland, Cruaud, Gavory, Doumenge, [Navascués](#) & Hardy (2010) CpDNA-based species identification and phylogeography: application to African tropical tree species. *Molecular Ecology* [doi:10.1111/j.1365-294X.2010.04917.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2010.04917.x)
28 citations (WoS/GS)
- P12 [Navascués](#), Depaulis & Emerson (2010) Combining contemporary and ancient DNA in population genetic and phylogeographic studies. *Molecular Ecology Resources* [doi:10.1111/j.1755-0998.2010.02895.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1755-0998.2010.02895.x)
21 citations (WoS/GS), Invited Review
- P13 [Navascués](#), Stoeckel & Mariette (2010) Genetic diversity and fitness in small populations of partially asexual, self-incompatible plants. *Heredity* [doi:10.1038/hdy.2009.159](https://doi.org/10.1038/hdy.2009.159)
7 citations (WoS/GS), highlighted in News and Commentaries section

- P14 Robledo-Arnuncio, [Navascués](#), González-Martínez & Gil (2009) Estimating gametic introgression rates in a risk assessment context: a case study with Scots pine relicts. *Heredity* [doi:10.1038/hdy.2009.78](https://doi.org/10.1038/hdy.2009.78)
14 citations (WoS/GS)
- P15 [Navascués](#) & Emerson (2009) Elevated substitution rate estimates from ancient DNA: bias of Bayesian methods under complex demographic scenarios. *Molecular Ecology* [doi:10.1111/j.1365-294X.2009.04333.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2009.04333.x)
47 citations (WoS/GS)
- P16 *[Navascués](#), Hardy & Burgarella (2009) Characterization of historical demographic expansions from pairwise comparisons of haplotypes using linked microsatellites. *Genetics* [doi:10.1534/genetics.108.098194](https://doi.org/10.1534/genetics.108.098194)
8 citations (WoS/GS)
- P17 [Navascués](#), Vendramin & Emerson (2008) The effect of altitude on patterns of gene flow in the endemic Canary Island pine, *Pinus canariensis*. *Silvae Genetica* 57:357–363
8 citations (WoS/GS)
- P18 Burgarella, [Navascués](#), Soto, Lora & Fici (2007) Narrow genetic base in forest restoration with holm oak (*Quercus ilex* L.) in Sicily. *Annals of Forest Sciences* [doi:10.1051/forest:2007055](https://doi.org/10.1051/forest:2007055)
13 citations (WoS/GS)
- P19 [Navascués](#) & Emerson (2007) Natural recovery of genetic diversity by gene flow in reforested areas of the endemic Canary Island pine, *Pinus canariensis*. *Forest Ecology and Management* [doi:10.1016/j.foreco.2007.04.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2007.04.009)
14 citations (WoS/GS)
- P20 [Navascués](#), Vaxevanidou, González-Martínez, Climent, Gil & Emerson (2006) Chloroplast microsatellites reveal colonization and metapopulation dynamics in the Canary Island pine. *Molecular Ecology* [doi:10.1111/j.1365-294X.2006.02960.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2006.02960.x)
40 citations (WoS/GS)
- P21 [Navascués](#) & Emerson (2005) Chloroplast microsatellites: measures of genetic diversity and the effect of homoplasmy. *Molecular Ecology* [doi:10.1111/j.1365-294X.2005.02504.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-294X.2005.02504.x)
40 citations (WoS/GS)

Open Data

- Data from P7. *Dryad Digital Repository*. [doi:10.5061/dryad.q42p7](https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.q42p7)
- Data from P8. *Dryad Digital Repository*. [doi:10.5061/dryad.67f8v](https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.67f8v)
- Data from P10. *Dryad Digital Repository*. [doi:10.5061/dryad.4j7q3s0t](https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.4j7q3s0t)
- Data from: [Navascués](#) (2005) Genetic diversity of the endemic Canary Island pine tree, *Pinus canariensis* (PhD thesis). *Dryad Digital Repository*. [doi:10.5061/dryad.7tr51](https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.7tr51)

Software (available at Zenodo or [GitHub](#))

- Vitalis, Gay & [Navascués](#) (2017) TempoDiff: a computer program to detect selection from temporal genetic differentiation. Software from P1. ([doi:10.5281/zenodo.375600](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.375600))
- [Navascués](#) (2017) DIYABCskylineplot: A suite of R scripts to perform an Approximate Bayesian Computation Skyline Plot. Software from P2. ([doi:10.5281/zenodo.267182](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.267182))
- [Navascués](#) (2017) LMSE: analisis of Linked MicroSatellite data to make inferences of demographic Expansions. Software from P16.
- [Navascués](#) (2017) Blue Caterpillar: Program to perform individual population assignment based on linked microsatellite data ([doi:10.6084/m9.figshare.1108018.v1](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.1108018.v1)).
- [Navascués](#) (2017) SIplusA: Simulation of populations with a mixed reproductive system of self-incompatibility and asexuality. Software from P13.

Conferences

11 contributions to national (Spain, France, UK) conferences (including 7 oral)
24 contributions to international conferences (including 6 oral)
12 posters available in FigShare

Student supervision

2015–2018 M. Jullien. **PhD student**. Adaptation and selfing: theoretical and empirical approaches using temporal surveys.
2013 A. Becheler. **MSc student**. Limits of genome scans of selection in selfing plants: a simulation study.
2013 M. Goudet. **MSc student**. Diversification of the olive tree (*Olea europaea*) in the Central Sahara and Macaronesia during the Quaternary.

Teaching

2014 Workshop on Inference of Demographic History from **Approximate Bayesian Computation (ABC)**. Département EFPA-INRA (Nancy, France). *Level: fellow researchers*
2009 Teaching assistant at laboratory sessions. Université Pierre et Marie Curie (Paris, France). *Level: undergraduate*
2006 Course: Data, Statistics and Data Analysis (Lab: Statistics with R)
Breeding and Conservation of Forest Genetic Resources: Source identification of forest reproduction material by means of assignment methods and molecular markers. III Curso Internacional INIA-AECI (Madrid, Spain). *Level: postgraduate*
2001–2005 Teaching assistant at laboratory sessions. University of East Anglia (Norwich, UK). *Level: undergraduate*
Courses: Molecular Biology and Genetics (Lab: Cytogenetics), Biodiversity (Lab: Protozoa, Invertebrate Locomotion), Evolution, Behaviour and Ecology (Lab: Population Genetics)

Evaluation

- 36 reviews for 18 scientific journals (review record available at [Publons](#), **Top Reviewer for Molecular Ecology 2013**) and for [Peerage of Science](#) (Performance 18.1/20, including a [featured review](#)).
- Member of the [Peer Community in Evolutionary Biology](#).
- Grant application reviewer for the Icelandic Research Fund (RANNIS, 2010).
- Thesis examination committee for M. Arenas (PhD, Universidad de Vigo 2010) and V. Noguerales (PhD, Universidad de Castilla La Mancha 2017).

Science outreach and communication

- **Film making** of “Life cycle of the liver fluke (*Fasciola hepatica*)” (2016, available on [YouTube](#), in French)
- Hosting a secondary school student in the lab to discover the profession of a scientist (“*Stage de découverte du milieu professionnel*”, 2011)
- Design and presentation of a stand about the “Biodiversity in the Farm” for the children's event *Spring Fling 2004* organized by the Royal Norfolk Agricultural Association at Norwich (UK)

5. Capacity of the Participating Organisations

Beneficiary: Uppsala University	
General Description	
Role and Commitment of key persons (supervisor)	Professor Mattias Jakobsson is the head of the lab. He will be responsible of the overall supervision of the project, including my integration in the lab and that appropriate training is available to me.
Key Research Facilities, Infrastructure and Equipment	<p>The host department has a support team composed by administrative staff, personnel officers, system administrator and an administration manager, which have experience managing European projects including Marie Skłodowska-Curie fellowships.</p> <p>Computing facilities will available at the Uppsala Multidisciplinary Centre for Advanced Computational Science (UPPMAX) which has a cluster with more than 2 000 000 CPU hours per month of total capacity.</p>
Independent research premises?	Research facilities are owned by Uppsala University and are wholly independent from other entities.
Previous Involvement in Research and Training Programmes	<p>Training:</p> <p>5 PhD students and 5 master students have completed their work at the lab</p> <p>Research:</p> <p>2012–2017 European Research Council Starting Grant</p> <p>2013 Wallenberg Academy Fellowship (7.5 million SEK)</p> <p>2015 Göran Gustavsson Prize (1.2 million SEK)</p>
Current involvement in Research and Training Programmes	<p>Training:</p> <p>Currently 7 PhD students and 2 postdocs working in the lab.</p> <p>Research:</p> <p>2013–2018 The Swedish Research Council’s Grant for Distinguished Young Researchers (18 million SEK)</p> <p>2014–2020 Atlas of Ancient Human Genomes in Sweden (35.4 million SEK)</p> <p>2016–2022 1000 Ancient Genomes (40.4 million SEK)</p>
Relevant Publications and/or research/innovation products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Günther, (17 authors) & Jakobsson (2015) Ancient genomes link early farmers from Atapuerca in Spain to modern-day Basques. PNAS, 112:11917–11922 • Schlebusch, (3 authors) Jakobsson & Broberg (2015) Human Adaptation to Arsenic-Rich Environments. Molecular Biology & Evolution, 32:1544–1555 • Skoglund, (3 authors) & Jakobsson (2014) Investigating Population History using Temporal Genetic Differentiation. Molecular Biology & Evolution, 31:2516–2527 • Skoglund, (13 authors) & M Jakobsson (2014) Genomic Diversity and Admixture differs for Stone-Age Scandinavian Foragers and Farmers. Science, 344:747–750 • Li & Jakobsson (2012) Estimating demographic parameters from large-scale population genomic data using Approximate Bayesian Computation. BMC Genetics 13:22

6. Ethical Issues

1. Human embryos & foetuses: The research project does not involve the use of human embryos or foetuses.

2. Human beings: The research project does not involve work with human beings.

3. Human cells or tissues: The research project does not involve work with human cells or tissues.

4. Personal data: The research project does not involve collection or processing of personal data. The project includes the analysis of human population genetic data collected in previous research projects by the hosting research team and other public data (secondary data). However, **these are not personal data because data subjects are not identifiable** (Article 2(a) of EU Directive 95/46/EC). These data were obtained from samples for which donors had given an informed consent and data were **completely anonymised** as part of the previous projects ethical protocols (all projects in Jakobsson lab have been approved by the Regional Ethical Review Board at Uppsala).

5. Animals: The research project does not involve work with animals.

6. Non-EU countries: There is no involvement of non-EU countries in any part of this project.

7. Environment, health & safety: The research project does not involve any activity that can be harmful for the environment or to the research staff. The work for this projects does not involve field work or laboratory experiments.

8. Dual use: The research project does not develop any technology, software or device that could have military applications or contribute to the proliferation of weapons of mass destruction.

9. Exclusive focus on civil applications: No military partners are involved in the research project which has an exclusive focus on civil applications. I foresee only applications to fundamental research programs in medicine, agriculture or conservation biology from the methods and knowledge obtained from the research project.

10. Potential misuse of research results: The methods and knowledge obtained from the research project cannot be used to harm humans, animals or the environment. Their application to purposes other than those described in the current research proposal would be limited to fundamental research and would not be unethical as far as I can tell.

11. Other ethics issues: I do not foresee any ethical issue or concern, in addition to those covered by the Ethics Issue Table, that could arise during our research project.

ENDPAGE

MARIE SKŁODOWSKA-CURIE ACTIONS

Individual Fellowships (IF)
Call: H2020-MSCA-IF-2017

PART B

“TimeAdapt”

This proposal is to be evaluated as:

EF-ST